

CHALLENGES OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN ZIMBABWE BETWEEN 1960 AND 2000

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Abstract:

This paper examines the main challenges which confronted Zimbabwe's tourism sector between 1960 and 2000. The Unilateral Declaration of Independence (UDI) in 1965 led to the imposition of sanctions in Rhodesia (now Zimbabwe). This development set the stage for a long period of international isolation at regional and global levels. The negative image resulting from this event undermined tourism in the country. This was followed by the prosecution of the armed struggle between 1966 and 1979. Security threats undermined tourist arrivals in the country especially after the shooting down of the viscount by members of the Zimbabwe African People's Revolutionary Army (ZIPRA) in 1978. Soon after independence in 1980, there was a surge in tourist arrivals into the country due to improved security within the country. However, the dissident menace in both Matabeleland and Midlands from 1982 to 1987 reversed the gains which had been realized at independence. After the signing of the unity, accord in 1987 there was a drastic improvement in security and this boosted tourist arrivals. However, most tourists came from neighboring South Africa and Zambia. Since some of them stayed with their relatives in Zimbabwe, they did not benefit tourist facilities such as hotels. Zimbabwe has drawn most of its tourists from its immediate neighbors while Kenya attracts tourists from as far as Europe and North America. In 2000, Zimbabwe's tourism industry suffered yet another dent with the launch of the Fast Track Land Reform Program (FTLRP). Due to the violent and bloody nature of the event, it attracted negative publicity from the media which further undermined the tourist arrivals in the country. To date the country has lagged behind Kenya in attracting European and North American tourists who bring the much needed foreign currency.

Keywords: tourism, security, wildlife, challenges, Zimbabwe

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1. Introduction

Tourism refers to 'the relationships and phenomena arising out of the journeys and temporary stays of people travelling primarily for leisure or recreational purposes' (1989:1). Tourism is a very fast growing industry only second to petroleum (Mapira, 2017). A distinction can be made between domestic and international tourism. While the former refers to people who visit places of attraction in their own country, the latter concerns those who visit other countries in order to view the various attractions and enjoy such benefits as a warm sunny climate, mountain climbing and going on a safari. At the global level, most tourism (80%) occurs among industrialized countries while 10% takes place within developing nations (Munowentu, 1996). On the other hand, 5% occurs between industrialized and developing countries while the remaining 5% occurs among developing countries.

Musasa and Mago (2014) explore challenges of rural tourism development in Zimbabwe focusing on Masvingo as a case study. They identify challenges to tourism development in Zimbabwe where political instability, community conflict, and lack of finance, poor marketing management, poor communication, and limited knowledge on running tourist enterprises prevail. The paper recommends that the government should develop rural tourism development strategies and policies. Tourism in rural areas is considered as the panacea for economic and social problems of rural communities through its capacity to generate earnings from tourists who come from far and wide. It also creates employment for the youths in various ways directly and indirectly. Tourism is considered a viable tool for sustainable rural development. However, the paper deplores the lack of a rural tourism promotion and development strategy, a situation which militates against sustainable growth and the development of rural communities.

In Zimbabwe, tourism contributes 11% to the gross domestic product (ZTV Morning News, 22 January, 2018). Between 1979 and 1981, the number of bed nights sold at the Victoria Falls and the Hwange National Park ranged from 32% to 43% and 40% respectively (Table 1).

Table 2: Tourist Visits to Victoria Falls and Hwange National Park (1979-1981)

Year	No. of bed nights available	No. of Bed nights 50	% of Total
1979	1 780 351	574 256	32
1980	1 829 479	776 880	43
1981	2 043 450	813 522	40

Source: Munowenyu (1996: 232)

Research shows that Kenya receives more foreign tourists than Zimbabwe. For example 63% of Kenya's tourists came from Europe while 18% were drawn from other African countries and 10% came from North America. Two facts emerge from this scenario. Firstly, far more tourists went to Kenya from outside Africa than those who came to Zimbabwe. Secondly, they spent far more foreign currency than those who went to Zimbabwe. This is due to the fact that Kenya has traditionally drawn its tourists from

Europe while Zimbabwe derives its tourists from South Africa (Munowenyu, 1996). This paper examines the challenges which have confronted tourism in Zimbabwe between 1960 and 2000.

2. Research Methods

This paper is based on two methods which include the perusal of secondary information as well as field observation. Secondary information was collected through research which focused on textbooks, journal articles, television programs and newspapers. Secondary information was aimed at building a theoretical framework for the whole study. It was followed by observations of the situation on the ground. This involved the collection of information from various tourist resorts in Zimbabwe. The collection of data for the research was conducted in January, 2018. The information collected was analyzed in order to produce the views that are expressed in this study.

3. Tourism at the Global Level

According to Pearce (1989), tourism is a multi-faceted and a geographically complex activity. This is because different services are sought and supplied at different stages from both origin and destination. In each region or country there is likely to be a number of origins and destinations. On the other hand, most places have both generating (origin) and receiving (destination) functions. Developing countries often do not generate many tourists even though small elites enjoy large amounts of such travel. In the real world, boundaries of tourism are not always neatly confined. On the supply side, facilities and services used by tourists may be purpose-built or designed for them or may be shared with other users. Facilities constructed for tourism range from resort hotels to ski-field access roads. Others such as cottages have become second homes while old canals and waterways have been restored for recreational boating. In some instances, tourism may supplement or complement an original activity. For example, Gothic cathedrals today attract the curious as much as the faithful.

Tourists may share their accommodation and transport with other travelers and take advantage of services and infrastructure provided essentially for the resident population. Classic tourist attractions include: coastal, alpine or thermal resorts. Major cities also attract millions of tourists as exemplified by London, Paris and Tokyo. Some rural areas also attract tourism even though they may be more dispersed and their organization less formal. At global level, tourism has emerged as a result of affluence in industrialized regions of the world where there is surplus to spend. Examples of such regions are: Europe, North America, Japan and more recently, China. Tourism has also emerged in countries of Eastern Europe and in some developing countries of Asia and Africa. In most developing countries, tourism has become a leading sector. It has also developed on a broad variety of physical environments such as low islands of the Pacific, in the heart of alpine Europe, in the countryside of the English Lake district and along the Mediterranean coastline. Today tourism has emerged to considerable

economic and social significance throughout the world. In 1986, the World Tourism Organization (WTO) estimated that about 340 million tourists generated receipts worth US \$115 billion. In general, there are more domestic than international tourists in most advanced nations.

Wawira (2-016) examines factors that influence tourism in Africa from an economic perspective. Africa's share of the global tourism market stands at 3.5%. Some 65.3 million arrivals reported in 2014 generated a whopping US\$43.6 billion in receipts and tourism accounts for 8.1% of Africa's total GDP (*World Travel and Tourism Council/ WTTC, 2014*). Tourism is considered a key pillar in driving accelerated economic development in Africa. There are several economic factors that influence tourism in Africa. For example, consumer demand by far determines tourism trends not only in Africa but globally. The pricing of various products and services in a destination plays a pivotal role in determining the volume of tourists. Sustained infrastructural development has also contributed to the solid growth of tourism in Africa. African governments invested in the building of road, rail and air transport networks, thus attracting the development of world class hotels. Developments and uptake of e-commerce has also influenced economic development in Africa. Online travel agents have made it easy and convenient for international tourists to make bookings and payments in the comfort of their homes thus accounting for US\$278 billion worth of business globally (*Euromonitor, 2013*). The growth and development in ICTs has a profound influence on tourism development in Africa by helping to bring light upon the great potential of African tourism attractions of a continent previously referred to as the 'dark continent'.

Mpofu (2013) analyses hindrances to optimum tourism development in sub Saharan Africa using document studies of tourist information bodies including the World Tourism Organization (WTO), United Nations World Tourism Organization Barometer (UNWTO), World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), Regional Tourism Organization of Southern Africa (RETOSA). Although the region is endowed with unique and diverse tourist attractions, it attracts less than 2% of the international tourists, thus it is the least visited region according to annual reports compiled by these tourist bodies. Several factors hinder the growth and development of tourism including poor accessibility, poor connectivity with major tourist generating regions within and outside the region, inadequate and poorly developed tourism infrastructure, inadequate and poor tourist facilities, political instability, widespread poverty, poor image, droughts and famine as well as the prevalence of diseases such as HIV and AIDS, malaria, cholera and yellow fever.

Mpofu's study recommends good governance as well as public private partnerships in order to improve tourist facilities and enhance the region's competitiveness. Tourism is a global people industry whose benefits are realized at both macro and micro level. At macro level, tourism drives economic growth, foreign exchange earnings and its contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP). At micro level, tourism creates jobs, redistributes wealth, generates income, improves the living

standards of the host community and helps to alleviate poverty as well as fostering a balanced development framework.

Mudzengi and Chiutsi, (2014) analyze the impact of socio political and macro-economic factors that influence ecotourism development in Zimbabwe using an ecotourism project on Mahenye in Chipinge. The study's major finding is that political and economic instability as well as bad international relations with tourist source regions have a strong negative impact on the competitiveness of ecotourism projects in Zimbabwe. The paper recommends the promotion of political and economic stability as a panacea to enhancing competitiveness of tourism in Zimbabwe.

3.1 Tourism in the SADC Region

The Southern African Development Community (SADC) contains 90% of mammal, amphibian and reptile species which are located in protected areas (Chenje and Johnson, 1994). This vast amount of natural wealth makes the region an attractive destination for both domestic and international tourists. In terms of space the region comprises about seven million square kilometers and up to one million is reserved for wildlife conservation (Table 2). Amounting to 15.66% of the region's total land area, it exceeds the minimum of 10% which is recommended by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the World Conservation Union (IUCN). Tanzania which has reserved 25% of its total land area has the largest area under this function. The area amounts to 237 005 square kilometers. On the other hand, Botswana reserves 39%.

Some of the major areas of wildlife in the region include Central Kgalagadi Game reserve (52 800 square kilometers) in Botswana, Selous Game Reserve (51 200 square kilometers) in Tanzania, Namib-Naukluft National Park (49 768 square kilometers) in Namibia and Kafue National Park (22 400 square kilometers) in Zambia (Table 2). Other areas of tourist attraction include the vast coastline which stretches from Angola, Namibia, South Africa to Mozambique. According to Chenje and Johnson (1994), the IUCN has suggested that some areas require extra protection. Firstly, they include those which are important for the maintenance of essential life-supporting processes such as catchment areas, migratory routes and wetlands. Secondly are those which support endemic plant or animal species. Finally, are those which represent areas of each ecosystem.

3.2 Protected Areas Categories in the SADC region

Within the SADC region, there are six categories of wildlife protected areas (Chenje and Johnson, 1994). Firstly, there are strict Nature Reserve/Wilderness Areas which contain outstanding or representative ecosystems, geological or physiological features and/or species. Such areas are meant for scientific research and/or environmental monitoring or large unmodified or slightly modified land, and/or sea.

Table 2: Protected Areas within the SADC region

Country	Country size	Protected area (%)	Size of protected area (sq km)
Angola	1 246 700	6.4	80 000
Botswana	581 730	39.0	226 875
Lesotho	30 350	0.2	68
Malawi	118 480	8.9	10 545
Mozambique	799 380	8.7	69 790
Namibia	824 290	13.5	111 414
South Africa	1 221 040	5.9	72 000
Tanzania	945 090	25.1	237 005
Zambia	752 610	29.8	224 078
Zimbabwe	390 580	12.9	50 385
Total	6 910 250	15.66	1 0 82 160

Source: Chenje and Johnson (1994: 160).

They retain their natural character and influence. Secondly, are the National Parks which are managed mainly for ecosystem conservation and recreation. They are designed to achieve at least three objectives which include:

- a) Protecting the ecological integrity of one or more ecosystems for this and future generations,
- b) Excluding exploitation or occupation inimical to the purposes of designation of the area, and
- c) Providing a foundation for spiritual, scientific, educational, recreational and visitor opportunities. All these should be environmentally and culturally compatible.

Thirdly, are the Natural Monuments which are managed mainly for conservation of specific features. Such areas are unique due to their inherent rarity, representative or aesthetic qualities or cultural significance. Fourthly, are the habitat/ species management areas. They are managed mainly for conservation through management intervention. They ensure the maintenance of habitats in order to meet the requirements of specific species. Furthermore, are the protected landscapes/seascapes. These areas are managed mainly for landscape/seascape conservation and recreation. Finally, are managed resources protected areas. They are managed mainly for the sustainable use of natural ecosystems. All these categories are attractive to both domestic and international tourists.

4. Zimbabwe's Tourism Industry over the Decades

The Zimbabwe National Statistical Agency (ZIMSTAT) (2015/16) report asserts that tourism has become one of the world's largest and fastest growing industries in the increasingly globalizing world. This exerts a powerful influence on economic development in many countries. Zimbabwe recorded growth in arrivals from 1.2 million in 2009 to 2.1 million in 2015. The positive performance is attributed to the vigorous marketing campaigns by the Ministry of Tourism and Hospitality Industry in partnership with the Zimbabwe Tourism Authority in promoting Zimbabwe as a safe

and unique destination to potential source markets. The report showed that the main factors that contributed to the negative visitor perception of the country included high prices, alleged harassment by traffic police, poor facilities, poor infrastructure and poor quality service delivery.

The Zimbabwe Tourism Authority (ZTA) was established by an act of parliament with a specific role of promoting tourism growth and development in Zimbabwe. ZTA keeps an updated database of the performance of the tourism sector in Zimbabwe and has all the important statistics on tourist arrivals, receipts and occupancy information on all local destinations. In its 2016 performance report, tourism at global level grew by 3.1% and was expected to grow by 3.4% and 3.7% in 2017 and 2018 respectively. International tourist arrivals grew by 3.9% from 1.189 billion in 2015 to 1.235 billion in 2016. The global arrival growth has been sustained since the year 2009. Arrivals into Africa also increased by 8.1% from 53.8 million in 2015 to 58.2 million in 2016. The market share of arrivals into Africa has remained very small at an average of 4% for the past decade (ZTA, 2017). Africa's share of the market is low and African countries need to come up with innovative ways to grow the market given its vast and unique tourist resources.

Globally tourism contributions are immense. Tourism contributes 10% to the Global GDP, one in eleven jobs come from tourism, and tourism generates US\$1.5 trillion in exports which is a contribution of 7% in exports. Furthermore, tourism makes up 30% of service exports, thus confirming the importance of tourism to the global economy (ZTA, 2017). Key identified issues to influence the global tourism are uncertainty over the United States policy, the growth of the Chinese economy and a weak Middle East economy.

In the year 2016, Zimbabwe received a total of 2,167,686 tourist arrivals, 5% up from 2,056,588 received in 2015. The positive growth was driven by the noteworthy upsurges in arrivals from all regions except for Europe and Oceania. The growth in arrivals into Zimbabwe was generally backed by growth in the country's traditional markets such as the UK and USA and compounded with the positive performance of African source markets (ZTA, 2017). Purposes of visit include business, education, indirect transit, shopping, leisure, visiting friends and relatives and others with leisure leading in terms of the numbers. Air and land (road and rail) are the mode of transport used by the tourists with 89% of the trips made by land and the remaining 11% by air (ZTA, 2017). Despite the 5% increase in tourist arrivals in 2016, receipts fell by 9% from US\$886 million in 2015 to US\$819 million in 2016 due to economic and financial challenges bedeviling the country.

ZTA (2017) reports that key events that impacted tourism in 2016 included: 2016 Summer Olympics at which the Zimbabwe Women's team made a maiden appearance thus raising awareness about Zimbabwe as it played Germany, Australia and Canada. Riots and protests led by the opposition political parties contributed to some negative publicity on the country resulting in some markets like the UK and Australia issuing travel warnings against Zimbabwe. Cash shortages had an influence on tourism in 2016. 80% of the tourist transactions are done in cash (ZTA, 2017) and this means that the

shortages negatively affected tourism receipts in 2016 as banks imposed cash withdrawal limits. This also contributed to negative publicity internationally and some countries had to issue travel advisories on the cash shortages issue thus deterring potential tourists from visiting Zimbabwe. Despite the 5% increase in arrivals in 2016, room occupancy fell by 1%. On the other hand, room occupancy fell from 47% to 46% in 2016.

Tourism is considered as a low hanging fruit for all nations especially among developing countries. It is considered as the largest and fastest growing industry globally contributing 20% to the global GDP and also employs more than 500 million people. Globally tourism has continued to grow reaching one trillion arrivals in 2017 (UNWTO Barometer, 2017). Africa has also experienced growth in tourism albeit in a skewed format with countries to the North and West benefiting more compared to those in the sub-Saharan region. As mentioned previously, in Zimbabwe, tourism presently contributes 11% to the gross domestic product, one in eleven jobs are provided by the tourism industry. It is also considered as one of the top anchors of the Zimbabwean economy together with agriculture, mining and manufacturing (ZIMASSET, 2013).

From 1980 to 1981, there was growth in both arrivals and receipts (ZTA, 2012). From 1982 to 1984 both arrivals and receipts took a nose dive due to the deteriorating security situation emanating from dissident activities in Matabeleland and Midlands. However, from 1985 to 1990 arrivals grew at a positive rate due to improvements in the security situation in the country (Table 3).

Table 3: Tourism in Zimbabwe from 1980 to 1990

Year	Tourist Arrivals	Tourism Receipts (US\$ million)
1980	237668	38.0
1981	313866	45.5
1982	276910	35.7
1983	230437	24.9
1984	254335	26.0
1985	303387	24.0
1986	318666	29.3
1987	339328	32.9
1988	412212	24.5
1989	435875	40.1
1990	582602	60.0

Source: ZTA (2012)

Several factors have influenced tourism in Zimbabwe over the years. They include: political conditions, climate, scenery, infrastructure, variety, costs and others such as miscellaneous factors (Munowenyu, 1996). Between the 1960s and 1970s, Rhodesia (now Zimbabwe) experienced negative political conditions. For example, the unilateral declaration of independence (UDI) by the white minority government in 1965 plunged the country into political turmoil which led to the imposition of sanctions (Mpofu, Muponda, Mutami and Tavuyanago, 2009). This event and the armed liberation

struggle which followed it between 1966 and 1979 dealt a major blow to the tourist industry in the country. By the late 1970s, the whole country had been plunged into civil strife thereby creating an unsuitable environment for tourism. The shooting down of the viscount in 1978 by the Zimbabwe African People's Revolutionary Army (ZIPRA) gave the country a very bad image from an aviation point of view thereby undermining tourism.

Tourists also look for favorable climatic conditions before visiting a country. A good example is sunny weather which is attractive to tourists from cooler climates. However, between October and April the country experiences wet conditions which tend to discourage tourists. Another attraction is scenery. Victoria Falls, Kariba Dam, Great Zimbabwe Monuments, the Eastern Border Highlands and Matopo National Park are very attractive. Other scenic spots include: Lake Mutirikwi and Tokwe-Mukosi in Masvingo Province. Another attraction is that of infrastructure which includes high-class hotel accommodation with efficient staffing, entertainment facilities such as casinos, cinemas and theaters, facilities for golf, fishing and game viewing. There is also a need for efficient operations to organize tours and to book facilities. Communications by road, rail, water and air should also be good. Over the years, Zimbabwe's road and rail infrastructure has broken down and calls for rehabilitation, a situation which paints a bad picture for tourists.

Variety is another attraction. The receiving country should also provide a wide variety of unique attractions such as wildlife, tribal dancing and different customs. For example, Zimbabwe's Hwange National Park and Game Reserves is well known and is quite close to the Victoria Falls (Munowenyu, 1996). In Kenya, traditional dancing has been developed greatly. On the other hand in Zimbabwean curios of soapstone, are of high quality. Tourists also require low costs in their bargains. For example, transport should be cheap to hire while hotel rooms should not be too expensive. However, since dollarization in 2009, Zimbabwe's currency has become too strong at the regional level. Finally, miscellaneous factors include: personal security and financial restrictions. In 1992 some 550 000 people visited Zimbabwe and brought Z\$52 402 700 in foreign currency. About 84% of these people came from other countries in Africa. Some 40% came from South Africa while 37% were from Zambia. Only 11% came from Europe with 6% from Britain while smaller numbers came from Asia, Australia and New Zealand (Munowenyu, 1996).

4.1 Challenges Confronting Zimbabwe's Tourism Industry

The benefits of tourism development include employment creation, generation of foreign currency earnings, use of renewable energy, participation and involvement, environmental education and awareness, education and awareness (Marunda and Munyanyiwa, 2014). These challenges include cultural erosion, adulteration of culture, commoditization of community culture, environmental degradation, unregulated and ill-defined natural resource ownership, inadequate project management skills amongst the communities as well as the lack of finance. Research has shown that tourism underpins four major important concepts:

Firstly, at the temporary travel there is a movement of people to an unusual place or destination with a clear intention of returning home within a short space of time.

Secondly, their motivation to travel excludes taking up residence or employment.

Thirdly, it is a sector of the economy or an industry. Finally, it involves a broad system of interacting relationships of people – visitors and hosts and the travel trade meeting as well as the needs of those travelers.

Middleton (2001) identifies four striking aspects of tourism that make it unique. Firstly, the product is invisible and cannot be tried out before purchase, as a result of the intangibility nature of the product. Secondly, it is consumed where and when it is produced, bringing in the idea of inseparability of the product. Thirdly, the place and people where it is produced are part and parcel of the product. Finally, demand for the product fluctuates between seasons of the year. Petersen (1991) states that communities have no idea whether the revenues they receive are as a result of their complaints about wildlife and tourists or whether they are due to the presence of wildlife and tourists.

It has already been noted that most visitors who come to Zimbabwe have originated from South Africa and Zambia. In general, this has a negative economic impact on the country. This is because most of these visitors have relatives in Zimbabwe and they tend to be accommodated by their next of kin instead of seeking for hotel accommodation. Such arrivals provide little or no benefits to tourist facilities in the country. Only visitors from Europe, Asia and America tend to benefit the country. Over the years, the government of Zimbabwe has been under sanctions especially since the FTLRP of 2000 (Bond and Manyanya, 2003). The bad image of the country at regional and global levels has had a damaging effect on tourism in general. At the same time, numerous companies have closed down in response to this crisis.

Efforts were needed to address the issue of international relations. The bad image syndrome persisted for over 30 years after independence. A new government would have to face these realities and if possible reverse them. However, this would require a return to democratic elections and the mending of damaged international relations. There is also a need to lure tourists from both Europe and America. However, such a drive would put the country into competition with East African countries such as Kenya which have traditionally attracted more Europeans and Americans. There is also a need to provide restitution to former white commercial farmers who lost their land in the wake of the FTLRP in 2000. According to a recent media report, some 4 100 former white farmers have tabled a US \$9 Billion claim for compensation by the government (*The Financial Gazette*, 25-31, January, 2018).

However, compensating the white farmers would require a lot of foreign currency, which is scarce in the country. Failure to do so would mean that the country remains with its stigma of international isolation. The newly resettled black farmers lack the money to compensate the white farmers who lost their land. On the other hand, the government is cash strapped and is struggling to do so. This dilemma does not have easy solutions. Furthermore, most roads in Zimbabwe are in a bad state. In order to

attract more foreign tourists there is a need to rehabilitate them. However, the main challenge is where to find money for such projects since the government is facing a cash crisis.

4.2 Tourism and the Pursuit of Sustainable Development

Sustainable Development (SD) refers to a type of development which seeks to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (WCED, 1991). Dating back to the Brundtland Commission of 1987, this concept has been widely spread and popularized to become a household concept at the global level. Since tourism in Zimbabwe heavily depends on South African and Zambian citizens, there is a need to broaden it to the global community. Zimbabwe can draw some lessons from countries of East Africa which depend more on tourists from Europe and North America (Munowentu, 1996). However, before this happens, there is a need to improve tourist facilities to global standards. The standards of hotels would have to be improved considerably while transport and communications would have to be upgraded to a point where they can compete at the global scale. The Harare-Beit Bridge road is set to undergo dualization while the National Railways of Zimbabwe is being rehabilitated.

Remote tourist attractions such as the Gonarezhou Game Reserve would have to be more accessible. This can be achieved through the construction of tarred roads which would make transport cheaper and easier. More hotels, restaurants and safaris would have to be established while car hire facilities would have to be developed in tourist resorts. One of the factors which inhibit the tourism industry in Zimbabwe has been the adoption of the US dollar as an official currency. As a result, Zimbabwe has become a very expensive tourist destination within the SADC region. It has become far more expensive for tourists to visit the country compared to other nations in the region. A good example is Victoria Falls where tourists find it cheaper to visit it through Zambia rather than Zimbabwe. If Zimbabwe could adopt a weaker currency, it would become more competitive in the attraction of tourists than it is today.

Another solution is to embrace democracy at the national level. In the past, most elections have been marred by violence and in some cases bloodshed (Bond and Manyanya, 2003). Such events have led to international isolation accompanied by the flight of capital to neighboring countries. This in turn has also led to the migration of Zimbabweans into foreign lands in search of employment opportunities. However, the re-introduction of democracy has its costs. If the ruling party (Zimbabwe African National Union-Patriotic Front/ ZANU-PF) embraces democracy, it must risk losing elections as it is likely to face stiff competition from opposition political parties such as the Movement for Democratic Change (MDC). The last time that it lost to the MDC in 2008, it resorted to a violent and bloody run-off (Mpofu, et. al, 2009). However, both SADC and AU refused to endorse the outcome leading to the formation of a government of national unity (GNU) at the beginning of 2009.

An Usaid report identifies challenges and issues regarding tourism development in Zimbabwe through a country wide study within the tourism and hospitality industry

(Sanderson, Nyamadzawo, Nyaruwata, and Moyo, 2013). The study participants included hotel managers, tour operation managers, and public sector executives. Tourism is crucial to the development of Zimbabwe and the study findings confirmed that the tourism sector makes immense contributions to the economic wellbeing of the country through employment creation, poverty alleviation, environmental conservation as well as diversifying the economy. The report asserts that tourism in Zimbabwe is based on natural resources, people, history, culture, amenities and superstructure. It found that the tourism sector is faced with a myriad of growth constraints including the lack of inter-governmental policy coordination, bad regulation, poor policy implementation, costly policy reversals, lack of internal airline connectivity, poor road network which requires urgent repair and rehabilitation, inadequate skills and lack of experience in running tourist facilities, weak domestic tourism promotion, and limited use of ICTs.

The study recommends a broad range of strategies to foster tourism growth and development in Zimbabwe and these are improving accessibility and connectivity by rehabilitating the road, air and rail transport systems, introduce smooth immigration policies that ensure easy passage of tourists at ports of entry such as improving the country's visa regime and reduce needless delays on police roadblocks. The study noted that to position the tourism sector for sustained growth there is need for a conducive and well-coordinated institutional framework and policy environment, establishment of a tourism revolving fund to support investments in the sector, improvement in internal airline connections, reforming the visa regime, human resource development, and improvement in the marketing coverage to both domestic and international markets.

Other factors affecting domestic tourism include the following: lack of awareness of holiday opportunities in the country, lack of a culture of taking leisure holidays, perception that going on holiday is expensive, a price sensitive market segment due to limited disposable income, lack of tour packages that are aimed at stimulating demand, domestic tourists paying the full price for holiday products compared to international tourists who access special rates used by tour operators, lack of coordinated promotion of domestic tourism by the players in the industry: ZTA, private sector, National Parks and Museums and Monuments each following their own strategies, poor road infrastructure and meal rates in hotels which are too expensive for the domestic market-breakfast costing 20/25 dollar per person at three star hotels. A family of four have to fork out \$100 which is enough for a week supplies at home, and national Parks prices that were introduced through the Parks and Wildlife Authority (Tariff of Fees). By-laws of 2012 which became effective in January 2013 are beyond the reach of a large segment of the domestic tourists. All these issues call for immediate attention if the tourist industry has to improve its capacity for future growth.

5. Conclusions

This paper has examined the challenges which confronted Zimbabwe's tourism sector between 1960 and 2000. The country has numerous tourist facilities which include the natural landscape, wildlife resources and cultural heritage sites. It also has important accommodation facilities such as hotels both in towns and cities as well as in recreational areas. However, the tourism industry has experienced several fluctuations during the period under study. Firstly, the declaration of UDI in 1965 led to international sanctions which gave a bad image of the country at the regional and global levels. This caused a dent on the tourism industry thereby undermining its prosperity. This was followed by the liberation struggle from 1966 to 1979. Due to escalating security threats during the war, only a few tourists could risk their lives by visiting the country. From 1980 to 2000, there was a surge in tourist arrivals into the country. However, most of them came from South Africa and Zambia. Since some of these tourists had relatives in the country, only a few visited hotels thereby undermining the viability of these facilities which had been established for this purpose. In 2000, the government of Zimbabwe embarked on the FTLRP which was marred by violence and bloodshed in some areas (Chibisa and Mapira, 2013). This event further damaged the country's image at both regional and global levels thereby further undermining tourism in the country. In general, three factors have negatively affected tourism in Zimbabwe. They include: UDI, the armed struggle of the 1960s and 1970s and finally, the FTKRP which was followed by international isolation through the imposition of sanctions.

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